

Uncovering the Innovation Productivity of Asian Countries: A Cluster Analysis Approach

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Abstract

The interplay of quality education in science and mathematics, university-industry collaboration in research and development, and a number of patents acquired dictates a country's level of innovation in the global economy. The study explored the innovation efficiency of thirty Asian countries with an attempt to group the nations with similar characteristics and uncover essential associations. Some variables from the Global Competitiveness Index 2017-2018 and the Global Innovation Index 2018 were used as multivariate inputs to the cluster analysis algorithm. Results revealed that there were three clusters of countries derived. Countries with low innovation, six in number, had small scores in the different variables that need to be improved. On the other hand, nations with high innovation, four in number, had the best scores in all the indicators. Further, the twenty countries with average innovation have to continue boosting its quality of Mathematics and Science education and university-industry partnership. Regression models of the different clusters were derived to supplement the results. Much is to be done on the patenting to be at par with the highly innovative countries in the world. In addition, to lessen the innovation gap, nations with high innovation may help the countries with low innovation productivity which is possible due to existing regional intergovernmental organizations in Asia like Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO), and the like.

Keywords: *Cluster Analysis; Innovation; Patent; Quality of science and mathematics education; University-industry research collaboration*

Introduction

Competitiveness and innovation embody two interrelated economic categories that complement one other. Through innovation, local products and services become competitive in the global economy (Sofrankova, Kiselakova & Cabinova, 2017). Many countries have the edge over their competitors, primarily attributed to their innovations, resulting from multiple factors, and it is difficult to evaluate based only on objective data (Kong, Zhou, Lui & Xue, 2017). Innovation is considered as a driver of economic growth and development. It

is essential for global competitiveness to rise. In day-to-day dialogue, innovation has been interchangeably used as invention and creativity. Creativity is thinking about new things, while innovation is producing new things. Furthermore, the invention is the initial occurrence of the concept, while innovation is the first try to carry it out into practice (Gerduri & Ramadani, 2010).

In spite of the various empirical literature on the factors of innovation, there is still no consensus as regards to the categories of factors that explain innovation (Amara & Landry, 2005). Pioneering research studies on innovation indirectly supposed that

innovation was the result of actions started by isolated businessmen or inventors (Sener & Saridogan, 2011). However, a number of existing literature considered three variables as major factors of innovation: quality of Science and Mathematics education, university-industry collaboration in research and development, and the number of patents. The World Economic Forum in its measure of global competitiveness considers the cited variables as innovation drivers of a country. However, innovation is not limited to science and technology, nor is it restricted to new products and processes. There are limited studies conducted on the given factors of innovation in the literature while taking into consideration Asian countries. Formal education remains to be the vital vehicle for cultivating the source of skills for innovation. Still, the traditional emphasis of policies in education for the improvement of innovation is through the teaching of Science and Mathematics, and to attract more students to Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (OECD, 2012). International evidence suggests that for innovation, it is essential for the improvements in the quality of education rather than its quantity (OECD, 2014). In recent years, advanced countries in the world put emphasis on improving the quality of education in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics as these disciplines are necessary to drive economic ambitions, support innovations and where knowledge-based economies depend on (STEM Education Review Group, 2016). Quinn (2009) stated that innovation starts in Mathematics and Science Education. He strongly supported the link between Mathematics and Science education, and innovation and competitiveness in the United States of America. Van Hiel and colleagues (2016) investigated the relationship between education and innovation in 96 countries around the world. Results revealed that education intensifies differences in liberalization values and innovation between developed and developing countries. Pieces

of evidence of cross-level interactions, consistently showing that individuals' level of education was related with growth in their liberalization values in societies with higher Human Development Index (HDI), whereas this relationship was limited in countries with lower Human Development Index. Countries with high HDI have better scores on innovation. Additionally, Sener and Saridogan (2011) cited that the most important aspect to achieve sustainable growth is through Science, Technology and Innovation-oriented competitiveness strategy. With the assumption, they investigated the effects of Science-Technology-Innovation oriented global competitiveness on the economic growth for the high-income OECD countries. Results revealed that countries which have science, technology, and innovation-oriented global competitiveness strategies have sustainable competitiveness and long-run growth. With the deterioration of industrial research laboratories in many countries, universities are tapped to play a vital role in the distribution of innovations in the economy. University research provides valuable inputs to industrial innovation, through which knowledge and technology are transferred from university researchers to the industry. Now, it is not surprising that firms increasingly pursue direct access to university knowledge through funding research projects (Hottenrot & Thorwarth, 2011). However, the acceptance of the task has been slow and restricted due to lack of incentives regarding merit and career advancement, due to patenting, licensing and commercialization activities (Sanberg, Holmstrom, Napier & Leven, 2015). Industry-university collaborations provide the best scaffold for innovation. The impact of university-industry interactions on development became even more significant since higher education institutions moved from a traditional role, focused on basic research and training, to a new part more involved in innovation and productive tasks such as technology transfer and patent licensing

(Mgonja, 2017). Furthermore, the role of universities as drivers for innovation has been gradually documented. United Kingdom government reports emphasized the role of university-business collaborations in driving local economic development (Economic and Social Research Council, 2017). Most of the university-industry collaborations became appreciated for innovation results, and many noteworthy benefits come from businesses with working relationships with universities. Fraser and Mancl (2017) specified that partnerships across a community such as university researchers and the industry, served as an alternative mechanism to stimulate innovative activities, usually through open innovation. With open innovation, it is suggested that significant ideas can originate from the inside or outside walls of the company and may drive to the market, still from the inside or outside premises of the firm (Chesbrough, Vanhaverbeke & West, 2006). A study of Maietta (2015) in Italy, examined the research and development collaboration between firms and universities to answer the role played by their partnership among the factors of product and process innovation in the Italian food and drink business. Multivariate probit analysis was used and data were gathered from four waves of the Capitalia survey. The results of the analysis revealed that research and development in university-firm collaboration determines process innovation and product innovation. In India, a study on the patterns, determinants, and effects of university-industry interactions towards innovation was conducted by Joseph and Abraham (2009). Data were drawn from a survey of companies covering different manufacturing industries and universities in four states of India. Findings showed that low levels of university-industry interaction resulted in poor innovative ability, while firms that collaborated with universities achieved a higher level of innovative ability. Patents, an outcome of the inventive process, play an increasingly important role in innovation and economic productivity. The growing usage of patents to safeguard inventions by industries and public research groups is closely linked to recent developments in innovation processes (OECD, 2004). Recent studies underscored that the patenting system may boost open innovation by motivating university-industry collaborations and markets for technology (Zobel, Balsmeier & Chesbrough, 2016). Patents may provide fences, however, it may lead to favorable relations among the actors of the innovation process (Pénin & Neicu, 2018). Patents are critical for innovation in the context like it can be used to produce income from licenses, boost partnerships, or be a form of advantage from competitors (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2013). Zobel and colleagues (2016) studied how patenting support or hamper open innovation. Evidence from new entrants in a solar industry was considered. The results revealed that, on average, patenting improve new entrants' number of open innovation relationships. In addition, the outcome of patenting is strongly positive for technology-intensive relationships, it turns out to be weaker as the technology intensity decreases, and goes negative for least technology-intensive relationships. Trying to understand the conditions that affect innovation, Crespi (2004) examined the determinants of innovation and technological change. Results revealed that the increase of research and development spending is not a sufficient factor of innovation. The importance of patents, market structure, and human capital had been considered due to the evolving concept that innovation is a multifaceted phenomenon and various aspects tend to impact it. With these, it is hypothesized that the interplay of quality education in science and mathematics, university-industry collaboration in research and development, and a number of patents dictate the level of innovation in the global economy. Specifically, the paper sought to cluster selected Asian countries to formulate system variable as indicators of innovation; and determine the characteristics of the grouped countries in terms of the cited

variables.

Framework of the Study

The Triple Helix Model (Leidesdorff & Etzkowitz, 1996) served as anchorage of the study. The model claimed that collaboration between university, industry, and the government is essential for innovation development. The Triple Helix emphasized that the possibility for innovation and economic development in a knowledge society lies in a more prominent role for the university in its quality of education and in the interplay of elements from university, industry, and government to generate new ideas for the production, transfer, and use of knowledge. In addition, Bednarzewska (2016) puts emphasis on the cooperation of entities representing the three groups (universities, business, and public administration) contribute to the competitiveness of a country.

Godoy (2018) stressed the value of education in innovation, through which education may affect economic growth. Mankiw and colleagues (1992) posited that education may increase the human capital within the labor force, which enhances labor productivity and therefore, produces an advanced level of output. Nelson and Phelps (1996) stated that education can ease the transfer of knowledge to successfully develop new technologies, which may lead to economic growth. Furthermore, the innovation ecosystem supported the idea that complex relationships are formed between innovation actors, which includes material resources and human capital that make up the institutional entities participating in the ecosystem (Jackson, 2011). Factors like quality of Science and Mathematics education, university-industry collaboration in research and development, and the number of patents are considered agents of the innovation ecosystem.

Methodology

The data sets in innovation index of the selected 30 Asian countries were taken from the Global Innovation Index 2018. The Global Innovation Index (GII) was founded by the prominent business school, European Institute of Business Administration (INSEAD) in 2007. Together with Cornell University, and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), a specialized agency of the United Nations, GI has become established as one of the most important and respected frameworks to evaluate key innovation indicators. Also, the data sets on quality of Mathematics and Science Education, University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Development and Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) Patents were taken from the Global Competitiveness Index 2017-2018 of the World Economic Forum. Cluster analysis was used in the study as a multivariate technique to group countries based on similarities in characteristics. The technique was also used to determine the innovation characteristics of the clustered countries in terms of their quality in Mathematics and Science education, university-industry collaboration in research and development and the number of patents. To supplement the results of the cluster analysis, the data gathered from countries belonging to every cluster were subjected to multiple linear regression analysis to explain the relationship of the three cited variables towards the innovation outcome. Regression models of innovation in every cluster were derived from the results of the multiple linear regression analysis.

Results and Discussions

Three clusters resulted from the analysis done. As shown in Table 1, the groups identified have twenty, six, and four countries respectively. Cluster 1, is a mixture of the different regions in Asia. Eight countries are coming from Western Asia and the Middle East, six comprised of Southeast Asian countries which include

the Philippines, and four from South-Central Asia. China from Eastern Asia and Russian Federation of Northern Asia also belong in the cluster.

The diverse countries in Cluster 1, have varying levels of income based on World Bank Income Group Classification. Eight high-income countries from Western Asia and the Middle East belong to the circle, while twelve countries are having upper-middle and lower-middle income are coming from Southeast, Eastern, Northern, and South-Central Asia. Furthermore, most of their gross domestic product percentage spending and allocation for research and development is on the average.

As presented in Table 2, these countries have the average performance in Mathematics and Science education quality, university-industry partnership in research, and a number of patents acquired. As a result, the cited countries have the average Global Innovation Index. The nations belonging in the first cluster need to continue its pursuit towards innovativeness to boost their global economy.

Countries like China, Russia, India, and the Philippines belong to this group. China's research and development expenditure have been growing steadily in the last decade despite their yet strong use of imported technologies, which led to an improvement of their university-industry research systems. The patenting system, however, is still lacking in some areas which might prevent further venture. Comparable to China, Russia's development in the previous years has also been intensely reliant on imported technologies. In the economic inauguration of the former Soviet Union, there are insufficient cases of university-industry partnerships (Mgonja, 2017). Furthermore, India's innovation is not brought by government inventiveness, big companies or government-funded research and development programs, but instead by the high-quality engineers and scientists which are estimated to be around 2.5 million

students every year graduating in the fields of information technology, engineering, and life sciences. India, however, still has challenges overcoming the divided tertiary education system, where universities are mainly engrossed on teaching and where government laboratories are concentrated exclusively on research activities (Mgonja, 2017). In the Philippines, innovation is necessary to boost its competitiveness by closing the gaps in innovation and sophistication factors, especially given that one of the most problematic aspects for doing business perceived by firms is their insufficient capacity to innovate (World Economic Forum, 2018). Countries with the least performance in all the indicators constituted the second cluster. Four of these countries were from South-Central Asia, one from Southeast Asia, and the other one from Western Asia and the Middle East. Five of these countries have lower-middle income, while only one has low income. Also, their gross domestic product allocation for spending on research and development is small. In return, the global innovation index is low.

The nations in this cluster have either less or zero number of patents based on Global Competitiveness Index 2017-2018. The result may be brought about by having less quality in Mathematics and Science education and meager university-industry collaboration in research and development. Bangladesh and Cambodia belong to this cluster. In Bangladesh, innovation is not their priority because they still have other problems that need an immediate response. The country aims to accelerate its growth to become a middle-income country by 2021 and continue its high leap of poverty reduction. Consequently, it seeks to increase the growth rate of its economy and improve the overall competitiveness of the economy (Kathuria & Malouche, 2015).

Cambodia has gone a long way in the implementation of new rules for economic growth in the past years. Still, the country has a low per capita income and is unable

Table 1. Clusters resulting from thirty Asian countries

	Number of Observations	Within Cluster Sum of Squares	Average Distance from Centroid	Maximum Distance From Centroid
Cluster 1	20	28.1962	1.06863	2.29833
Cluster 2	6	4.3425	0.76711	1.48130
Cluster 3	4	9.2183	1.40409	2.22325

Cluster 1 Bahrain; Brunei Darussalam; China; Cyprus; India; Indonesia; Iran; Kazakhstan; Kuwait; Malaysia; Oman; Philippines; Qatar; Russian Federation; Saudi Arabia; Sri Lanka; Thailand; Turkey; United Arab Emirates; Viet Nam

Cluster 2 Bangladesh; Cambodia; Kyrgyzstan; Nepal; Pakistan; Yemen

Cluster 3 Israel; Japan; Korea, Rep. ; Singapore

Table 2. Cluster characteristics of innovation from Asian countries

Variable	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Grand Centroid
Quality of Math and Science Education	4.3500	3.2333	5.2500	4.2466
University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Development	3.8450	2.7833	5.0250	3.7900
Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) Patents	1.1006	1.0000	5.3948	1.6530
Global Innovation Index	3.8786	2.1252	6.6276	3.8944

Table 3. Regression models of the three clusters

Cluster	Regression Model	R-squared	p-value
1	Global Innovation Index = -2.30 + 0.361 University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Development + 6.12 Patent – 0.448 Quality of Science and Mathematics Education	68.8%	0.000
2	Global Innovation Index = -7.8 + 0.346 University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Development + 7.5 Patent + 0.455 Quality of Science and Mathematics Education	35.01%	0.000
3	Global Innovation Index = 7.237 + 0.002 University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Development – 0.1696 Patent + 0.056 Quality of Science and Mathematics Education	100%	0.000

to finance key economic fundamentals, such as infrastructure and services. Investments are needed to move up the value-added hierarchy, to improve productivity, growth, and development (UNDP Cambodia, 2009).

Cluster 3 countries belong to the top most innovative nations in the world. These countries have the best scores in the different indicators. Two of these countries belong to Eastern Asia, one from Southeast Asia and the other one from Western Asia and the Middle East. The gross domestic product allocation for spending on their research and development projects are very high. Singapore, Korea, Israel, and Japan are leading innovators in Asia having very high innovation index, most number of patents, remarkable quality education in Science and Mathematics and robust university-industry collaboration in research and development.

Table 3 shows the regression models of the different clusters. Countries in the first cluster with average indicators, like the Philippines, may continue to strengthen its university-industry collaboration in research and development to acquire a number of patents. It is reflected in the table that for this cluster the increase in a number of patents will boost the innovation index at its highest point. On the other hand, the negative sign of the quality of Science and Mathematics does not necessarily mean to decrease in its quality but to be sustain the quality. The model reveals that these countries already have a good quality of education that can be translated into innovation. The challenge is much on increasing productivity on the other two variables. Further, the regression model of the first cluster accounts for 68.8% of the variance of the response variables with a p-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant.

Second cluster countries, whose indicators are low, need to double their time in increasing their university-industry research collaboration to have more patents. The quality of Science and Mathematics in these countries need to improve to produce more innovative outputs.

On the contrary, the highly innovative nations in the third cluster have to sustain the different indicators. It may continue improving its university-industry research partnership and quality education in Science and Mathematics to remain at the top. However, the negative sign for patenting indicates that for these countries, it is not advisable to have an extreme number of patents because there may come a time that the countries innovation may reach its saturation point. They may approach their limitations, and it may pull the innovation index down. The regression models of cluster 2 and 3 account for 35.01% and 100% of the variances of the response variables respectively, which are statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000.

The derived regression models characterized the different clusters, in a way that, the resultant groups have similarities and differences. The similarity of different clusters indicates the direct relationship between them. The first and second clusters suggest that additional university-industry research partnership and an increase in the number of patents will enhance the innovation productivity. Looking into the second and third clusters, they are alike in the manner that enrichment in the quality of Science and Mathematics education and strong university-industry research partnership will contribute to the advancement of innovation.

Differences in the regression models are clearly emphasized in the strengths and weaknesses of the different clusters. Clusters 1 and 3 have inverse relationships in patenting and quality education in Science and Mathematics. An increase in the number of patents will make cluster 1 more innovative. However, it will cause a decrease in the innovation turn-out of group 3. Further, an increase in the quality of education in Science and Mathematics will depreciate the innovation cluster 1 but will escalate cluster 2's innovation.

Conclusions

The study explored the innovation performance of thirty Asian countries in terms of their quality education in science and mathematics, university-industry collaboration in research and development, and number of patents. With cluster analysis, nations with similar characteristics in the three variable were grouped accordingly. Essential associations and patterns were uncovered to provide information in improving a country's innovation performance and be considered a highly innovative country, which were not documented in previous literature.

Based on the results, the interaction of quality education in science and mathematics, university-industry collaboration in research and development, and a number of patents dictated the level of innovation in the global economy. Those Asian countries having high performance in the different indicators were clustered accordingly. Similarly, those Asian countries with average and low performance, regarding the set variables, were grouped accordingly. Their regression models suggest actions to be made by the different variable to optimize the innovation productivity.

Countries with low innovation have to catch-up with the countries having average and high innovation. There is a need to invest in the quality of Mathematics and Science education, university-industry partnership in research and development and increase the number of patents. Those countries that have average innovation have to continue boosting its quality of Mathematics and Science education and university-industry partnership. Much is to be done on the patenting to be at par with the highly innovative countries. The Philippines, as part of the average innovative countries in Asia, has to live with the challenge.

The highly innovative countries have to sustain its performance in the different indicators. However, it is recommended not to dash on the acquisition of numerous patents for the countries not to reach its

the saturation point untimely. Also, the more patents the highly innovative countries produce, the bigger innovation gap it brings to the economic society. It is suggested that highly innovative countries help the low and average ones to improve their innovation productivity, rather than focus much on being more. Associations and organizations of countries in Asia, like ASEAN, SEAMEO and the like, may initiate the movement with the presence of the highly innovative ones. Each country has to be particular on the factors that improve their innovation performance to be able to withstand the twenty-first century demands. The country that lags behind innovation has to continue initiate programs, projects and policies to be at par with the highly innovative nations in the world. With innovation, global competitiveness is at hand and economic progress follow.

Recommendations

The study is not without limitations. There are various variables affecting the innovation performance of different countries. However, the present study considered only three: quality education in science and mathematics, university-industry collaboration in research and development, and number of patents. Future researchers may add more variables of innovation performance to have more comprehensive results.

The study made use of cluster analysis, which is more focused on grouping the similarities of different countries in terms of the given variables. Other multivariate statistical techniques may be utilized to further enrich the results the study. Similar studies on countries innovation performance may be conducted on a larger scope which is not limited to Asia, different perspective, other variables may be considered, and on a variety of research designs. Innovation in the field of education may be explored for future researches.

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References Cited

- Amara, N., & Landry, R. (2005). Sources of information as determinants of the novelty of innovation in manufacturing firms: evidence from the 1999 statistics Canada innovation survey. *Technovation*, 25, 245–259. doi: 10.1016/S0166-4972(03)00113-5.
- Bednarzewska, K. (2016). University-Business-Government the Triple Helix Model of Innovation. Managing Innovation and Diversity in Knowledge Society Through Turbulent Time: Proceedings of the MakeLearn and TIIM Joint International Conference 2016, ToKnowPress. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/h/tkp/mklp16/109.html>
- Chesbrough, H., Vanhaverbeke, W., & West, J. (2006). *Open innovation: Researching a new paradigm*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Crespi, F. (2004). Notes on the determinants of innovation: A multi-perspective analysis. *Fondazione Eni Enrico Mattei (FEEM) Working Paper* No. 42.04. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.524503>.
- Economic and Social Research Council (2017). *More innovation through university-business collaboration*. Retrieved from <https://esrc.ukri.org>.
- Fraser, S., & Mancl, D. (2017). Innovation through collaboration: Company-university partnership strategies. 2017 *IEEE/ACM*
- Gerduri, S., & Ramadani, V. (2010). The impact of innovation into the economic growth. *Munich Personal RePEc Archive Paper* No. 22270. Retrieved from <https://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/22270/>.
- Godoy, M. (2018). The Many Factors of Growth: How Innovation Plays a Part. *UC Merced Undergraduate Research Journal*, 10(2). Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7242937s>
- Hottenrot, H., & Thorwarth, S. (2011). Industry funding of university research and scientific productivity. *ZEW Discussion Paper* No. 10-105. Center for European Economic Research. Retrieved from <http://ftp.zew.de/pub/zew-docs/dp/dp10105.pdf>
- International Renewable Energy Agency (2013). *Intellectual property rights: The role of patents in renewable energy technology innovation*. Retrieved from <https://www.irena.org/publications/2013/Jun/Intellectual-Property-Rights-The-Role-of-Patents-in-Renewable-Energy-Technology-Innovation>.
- Jackson, D. (2011). What is an innovation ecosystem? Arlington, VA: National Science Foundation. Retrieved from http://erc-assoc.org/sites/default/files/topic_s/policystudies/DJackson_Innovation%20Ecosystem_03-15-11.pdf
- Joseph, K., & Abraham, V. (2009). University-industry interactions and innovation in India: patterns, determinants, and effects in select industries. *Seoul Journal of Economics*, 22 (4), 467-498. Retrieved

- from <http://www.sje.ac.kr/upload/repec/wpaper/c154f120a7645e7eb9857f21def650bf.pdf>
- Kathuria, S., & Malouche, M. (2015). Toward new sources of competitiveness in Bangladesh: key findings of the diagnostic trade integration study (English). *Directions in development trade*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group. Retrieved from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/22712>.
- Kong, D., Zhou, Y., Lui, Y., & Xue, L. (2017). Using the data mining method to assess the innovation gap: A case of industrial robotics in a catching-up country". *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 119, 80-97. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2017.02.035>
- Leidesdorff, L., & Etzkowitz, H. (1996). Emergence of a triple helix of university-industry-government relations. *Science and Public Policy*; 23, 279-86. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1093/spp/23.5.279>
- Maietta, O. (2015). Determinants of R&D university-firm collaboration and its impact on innovation: A perspective from the Italian food and drink industry. *2015 International Conference of Agriculture Economists*. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/p/ags/iaae15/225668.html>.
- Mankiw, N. G., Romer, D., & Weil, D. (1992). A contribution to the empirics of Economic growth. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*.
- Mgonja, C. (2017). Enhancing the university-industry collaboration in developing countries through best practices. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT)*, 50(4). Retrieved from <http://ijettjournal.org/archive/ijett-v50p235>.
- Nelson, R. R., & Phelps, E. (1966). Investment in Humans, Technology Diffusion and Economic Growth. *American Economic Review* 56(2), 69-75. doi:10.12691/jbms-1-6-3.
- OECD (2004). *Patents and innovation: Trends and policy challenges*. Paris: OECD Publishing. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264026728-en>.
- OECD (2012). *OECD science, technology and industry outlook 2012*. Paris: OECD Publishing. Retrieved from https://doi.org/10.1787/sti_outlook-2012-en.
- OECD (2014). *Science, technology and innovation in Vietnam. OECD Reviews of Innovation Policy*. Paris: OECD Publishing. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264213500-en>.
- Pénin, J., & Neicu, D. (2018). Patents and open innovation: Bad fences do not make good neighbors. *Journal of Innovation Economics & Management*, 25,(1), 57-85. doi:10.3917/jie.025.0057.
- Quinn, G. (2009, October 21). *Innovation Starts with Math and Science Education*. Retrieved from <http://www.ipwatchdog.com/2009/10/21/innovation-starts-with-math-and-science-education/id=6754/>
- Sanberg, J., Holmstrom, J., Napier, N., & Leven, P. (2015). Balancing diversity in innovation networks: Trading zones in university-industry R&D collaboration. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 18(1), 44-69. doi: 10.1108/EJIM-09-2013-0088
- Sener, S., & Sarıdogan, E. (2011). The effects of science-technology-innovation on competitiveness and economic

growth. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 24, 815–828. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/>.

Sofrankova, B., Kiselakova, D., & Cabinova, V. (2017). Innovation as a source of country's global competitiveness growth. *SHS Web of Conferences*. doi: 10.1051/shsconf/20173901026.

STEM Education Review Group (2016). *STEM education in the Irish school system*. Retrieved from <https://www.education.ie/en/Publications/Education-Reports/STEM-Education-in-the-Irish-School-System.pdf>

UNDP Cambodia (2009). *Annual report 2009*. Retrieved from <http://www.kh.undp.org/content/cambodia/en/home/library/annual-report.html>

Van Hiel, A., Van Assche, J., De Cremer, D., Onraet, E., Bostyn, D., & Haesevoets, T., (2018). Can education change the world? Education amplifies differences in liberalization values and innovation between developed and developing countries. *PLoS ONE*, 13(6): e0199560. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0199560>

World Economic Forum (2018). *Global Competitiveness Index Report 2018*. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-global-competitiveness-report-2018>

Zobel, A., Balsmeier, B., & Chesbrough, H. (2016). Does patenting help or hinder open innovation? Evidence from new entrants in the solar industry. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 25(2), 307–331. doi:10.1093/icc/dtw005